

Cost-effective implementation of renewable energy sources in livestock barns

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Abstract

Livestock barns have a high electrical and thermal energy demand, attributed to guaranteeing comfortable conditions and indoor air quality for the animals. Currently, these demands are typically met by extracting electricity from the grid and combusting fossil fuels (oil or gas). Renewable energy sources have already been developed and are being used extensively for residential applications. The cost-effective implementation of the sustainable technologies in livestock farms is however not straightforward. Therefore a numerical model was developed where the use of these technologies can be simulated. The model allows to determine the life cycle cost of the installation and the annual carbon dioxide emissions. The application of the model is demonstrated on a renewable energy system for a pig stable in Belgium.

1. Introduction

To assure the comfort conditions for the animals, livestock barns can be equipped with a heating, cooling and ventilation system. These systems however cause the farms to have a high electrical and thermal demand. In Belgium, the pig sector is responsible for 10% of the total energy use of the farming sector [1]. Of this energy demand, 49% was provided by the combustion of fuel oil (in 2016). Fossil fuels however contribute to global warming by emitting greenhouse gases (like carbon dioxide, CO₂), are expensive and have a high price volatility. In order to allow the phase out of fossil fuels, renewable alternatives are available on the market. Fuel boilers can be replaced by heat pumps and heat and electricity can be generated locally with photovoltaic (PV) solar panels, solar thermal (ST) collectors, PVT-panels (a hybrid system combining photovoltaic panels and thermal collectors) and wind turbines. Furthermore, to deal with the intermittent behaviour of solar radiation and wind, storage is possible with batteries (electrical storage) or hot water tanks (thermal storage). While these systems have already found their way into residential and commercial buildings, they are hardly adopted by the livestock sector.

If it is economically feasible, farmers are willing to invest in renewable systems. The main problem is however that the loads are very farm specific, so both the farmers and the installers have difficulties designing a system for a livestock barn. In this paper, a numerical simulation model is therefore described which allows to evaluate the performance of a system and to assist with optimizing the design.

2. Methodology

In order to design farms with minimized greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, a model was developed in Python where the energy performance and GHG emissions (related to using gas or electricity from the grid) of a barn can be simulated for an entire year. The electrical energy demand and thermal energy demand (possibly on different temperature levels) are given as inputs to the model with a resolution of one hour. Also weather data (outside temperature, solar irradiation and wind velocities) and energy prices (from before the energy crisis) are provided to the model as input.

Different renewable energy system (RES) technologies are implemented in the model: heat pumps, solar energy, wind energy, thermal storage and electrical storage. For every time step of the simulated period, the model calculates the renewable energy potential and compares it to the energy demand. Generated energy (electrical and thermal) is first maximally used on site. When there is an excess of energy generation, this is maximally stored. When electrical storage is at full capacity, electricity is injected into the grid. As no thermal grid is considered, any excess heat is discarded. When solar and wind energy are not sufficient to cover the loads, the energy deficit is taken from the grid.

Based on the energy flows calculated by the model, the total electricity and gas taken from the grid for a barn with a certain RES installation are found. This allows to determine the yearly operational costs and equivalent GHG emissions. Based on the installation costs (IC_0) and the yearly energy costs (EC_i), the lifecycle cost (LCC) is calculated according to Equation 1:

$$LCC = IC_0 + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{EC_i + IC_i}{(1+r)^i} \quad 1$$

In this equation, n represents the simulated time period (20 years was chosen). The estimated lifetime of the equipment is taken into account. When some technology needs to be replaced in year i , the investment cost is added again with the term IC_i . All costs that are not initial costs, are discounted with a discount rate r (6% was used).

In order to minimize the computational time of a simulation, the level of detail in the models of the components was kept low. Furthermore, higher levels of details require more inputs which are not always available. For estimating the cost of the technologies, conversations were held

with installers and online queries were performed. Based on the results, some rudimental correlations were drafted. All details about the model can be found in Deliverable 2.2 of the RES4LIVE project [2].

3. Case study

The model was used to evaluate the RES possibilities for an existing pig farm in Belgium. The farm is exploited by the Flemish Institute for Agriculture and Fisheries (ILVO) and yearly keeps about 105 sows, 600 piglets and 750 finishing pigs. The barn is mechanically ventilated. The supply air can be heated with tubes in which water at 70°C flows. Also underfloor heating, with water at 40°C, is present. No cooling systems are installed. Hot water is supplied with a condensing gas boiler of 60 kW. The total electricity demand is approximately 107 MWh/y, while the heat demand is 212 MWh/y. For this barn accurate energy demands per month and per year are available. Additionally, a realistic heat demand profile was developed earlier [3].

3.1. Simulations

Firstly, a selection of 6 different cases will be compared. The first case is the current system installed on the existing farm, consisting of only a gas boiler. As the goal is to minimize GHG emissions, all other cases will use a heat pump (HP), possibly combined with solar or wind energy. A heat pump is used because it is assumed that the emissions related to using electricity (either generated locally or taken from the grid) are lower than those of using gas. The different cases are:

- Case 1: Gas boiler without RES (System currently installed)
- Case 2: One high temperature HP (55 kW) and one low temperature HP (15 kW)
- Case 3: Same as Case 2 with the addition of 500 m² of PV panels
- Case 4: Same as Case 2 with the addition of 500 m² of ST panels
- Case 5: Same as Case 2 with the addition of 500 m² of PVT panels
- Case 6: Same as Case 2 with the addition of a 15 kWn wind turbine

An area of 500m² for solar energy was selected because this is approximately what is available on the barn roof.

As it is likely that the optimal system design consists of a combination of all technologies, a design space was defined using the technologies with various sizes. The combination of all possibilities results in a total of 165 888 possible designs, which will all be simulated (although some combinations are not relevant; e.g. thermal storage without solar collectors).

4. Results

4.1. Selected RES designs

In Figure 1, the resulting LCCs and GHG emissions are shown for the 6 selected designs. All LCCs and emissions are relative to the LCC and emissions of Case 1. This case has an LCC of € 642 000 and GHG emissions of 77 ton/y (not shown in Figure 1). It can be observed that all cases have significantly lower GHG emissions than the current system. Only a heat pump already results in a reduction of 50.3%, while the maximal reduction is obtained in the combination with PVT panels (62.9% reduction). The LCC of all cases is similar to the LCC of Case 1 (-7.2% to +16.3%). Case 3, with heat pumps and PV panels, has the lowest LCC, while Case 4, with heat pumps and solar collectors has the highest LCC. It can be concluded from this comparison that significant GHG emission reductions are possible compared to the current situation. This can even be done with a reduced LCC. The systems here are however not yet optimally sized and don't combine different RES in one system. This combination of different technologies is discussed in the next sections.

Fig. 1: LCC and GHG emissions of the selected cases, relative to Case 1.

4.2. Design space exploration

Next, the results of the design space exploration are discussed. An overview of the results is given in Figure 2, where the annual GHG emissions for a given design are represented as a

function of the investment cost of that design. The colour of the points indicates the relative difference between the LCC of a design compared to the LCC of the current installation (gas boiler, no RES). For clarity, only designs with an investment cost below € 500 000 are shown. The design of the current installation, with only a gas boiler and no RES technologies, is represented by the upper left point (minimal installation cost and maximal GHG emissions).

Fig. 2: GHG emissions and installation cost for the entire design space, with the LCC difference indicated in color.

The results in Figure 2 show a clear distinction in two clouds of data points, with emissions below and above approx. 40 000 kg/y. All data points contained in the upper cloud represent designs without a heat pump, using a gas boiler for heating, while points in the lower cloud all use one or two heat pumps. As the purchase cost of a heat pump is higher than that of a gas boiler, the lower cloud starts at higher installation costs than the upper cloud. It can be seen that RES significantly reduce GHG emissions, as the introduction of a only a heat pump already decreases the emissions by almost 50%. Additionally, it can be seen that by introducing RES, the LCC can either increase (LCC difference $> 0\%$) or decrease (LCC difference $< 0\%$), compared to the installation without RES. Using only a heat pump (without other RES) has an LCC that is +5.5%. The introduction of other sustainable technologies generally decreases the LCC. According to the simulations of the design space, when using a heat pump, a total investment of € 112 000 is required to achieve a lower LCC than the current design. With even

higher investments in RES, LCC reductions of more than 20% are possible. These however require (for the case where heat pumps are used), upfront investments of at least € 252 000.

4.3. Future work

The results discussed above does not clarify what kind of combinations result in minimized LCC and GHG emissions. Therefore, a more thorough analysis is necessary. Furthermore, in this paper, only one farm was used to demonstrate the use of the model and no sensitivity analysis was presented. A more detailed analysis was already performed in the framework of the RES4LIVE project. The interested reader is referred to Deliverable 2.2 of this project.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, a model was presented that allows to evaluate the performance of a RES system for a livestock barn. A system is evaluated by calculating the lifecycle costs and the yearly greenhouse gas emissions, using the electrical and thermal demand, as well as weather data as inputs. Simulations are performed for 20 years with a time step of 1 hour, taking into account the estimated lifetime of the used technologies. The considered technologies are heat pumps, photovoltaic panels, solar collectors, PVT panels, wind turbines, electrical storage and thermal storage. Simplified models of all these technologies are implemented in the model.

The model is applied to an existing pig farm with a yearly electrical demand of 107 MWh and a thermal demand of 212 MWh. First, 6 selected RES systems are compared. These clearly show that large GHG emission reductions are possible, combined with a reduction of the LCC. In order to minimize both GHG emissions and LCC, an entire design space was simulated. Using a heat pump will always result in lower GHG emissions, and certain designs give an LCC 20% lower than the current system (a gas boiler).

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